

Metabolic syndrome: the presence of inflammatory mechanisms in abdominal obesity is undeniable, gene therapy using nanoparticles and adenoviruses technologies is promising

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Abstract- The metabolic syndrome (MetS) is a key risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVDs) MetS affects about 34% of individuals in the United States. The presence of inflammatory mechanisms in abdominal obesity is undeniable. This indicates that the immune system has been activated, most likely as a result of the activation of pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) PRRs are located in innate immune cells and are responsible for detecting viral diseases in the body. PRRs (TLRs and NLRs) are thought to play a part in the pathophysiology of MetS, and targeting TLR4 receptors has been shown to assist with chronic conditions. Gene polymorphisms in humans have unexplained origins and effects. The main contributor to MetS problems caused by inflammasome 22 is the alteration of pro-inflammatory cytokines into their bioactive forms. The Food and Drug Administration has approved statins for lowering LDL cholesterol. In human atherosclerotic lesions, TLR1, TLR2, and TLR4 levels are the most common, and they mediate insulin resistance, which is at the heart of MetS. Hypertension is a MetS comorbidity that has a strong connection to TLR signaling.

The majority of chronic cardiovascular disorders are multifactorial, with many genetic and environmental factors at play. Adenoviruses can be used to produce gene therapy using nanoparticle technology. Cell proliferation, organogenesis, and metabolic function have also been shown to be influenced by peptides and micropeptides. Metallic, ceramic, and non-metal lattices have recently shown good proof-of-concept in targeted cancer therapy and are gaining acceptance in cardiovascular medicine. Because of the docking of subunits and regulatory peptides, the NOX family of enzymes may be a candidate for peptide therapies. The term "nanoparticle" encompasses a broad range of nanoscale structures

I. INTRODUCTION

The metabolic syndrome (MetS) is a major factor in the development of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), especially in adults (aged 18 and up) 1. In the United States, nearly 34% of people in this age group are affected by this condition. 2. To better understand how MetS and cardiovascular disorders interact, consider the different risk factors associated with this disease, such as hyperglycemia/insulin resistance, elevated blood pressure, dyslipidemia, and, especially, abdominal obesity. 3. Both risk factors are signs of the initiation of MetS, as well as the likelihood of CVDs 1,3. Previous findings have suggested that abdominal obesity is one of the most significant metabolic markers associated with MetS. 4,5 points 71.6 percent of adults in the United States are overweight, and 39.8 percent are obese, according to estimates. 6. Inflammatory pathways are clearly present in abdominal obesity 7, and inflammation is one of the main mechanisms discovered in MetS patients. 8.9/10 Notably, it means that the body has launched an immune response, likely caused by the activation of pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) 8. PRRs are responsible for identifying infectious infections in the body and are found in innate immune and non-professional immune cells. In chronic pathologies 10, such as MetS 8,11, these receptors also drive the identification of signals and/or cell molecules associated with cellular stress and injury.

PRRs play an important part in mediating the innate immune response in a number of ways. 10. Toll-like receptors (TLRs) and NOD-like receptors (NLRs), which are transmembrane and cytoplasmic receptors, respectively, are two of the most important receptor groups implicated in metabolic risk factors. When these receptors are triggered, they start signalling cascades that trigger the inflammatory reaction linked to several of the MetS 8 risk factors. The inflammasome complex, as well as essential cell signaling proteins like NF- κ B and mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), are then activated 8,11. As a result, manipulating these receptors may be an important method for treating MetS complications. This analysis will address recent advancements in our understanding of the interaction between PRRs and MetS, as well as the effects of therapeutics that exploit these receptors for the treatment of MetS complications. Korean Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology

II. SIGNALING MECHANISMS OF PRRS IN METS

Humans have evolved multiple recognition mechanisms to detect exogenous and endogenous ligands 12. Pattern recognition receptor PRRs, which can be located in a cell's membrane or cytoplasm, are crucial components of these recognition systems. Exogenous and endogenous ligands, such as PAMPs and DAMPs (pathogen and damage-associated molecular patterns, respectively), are believed to be recognised by these receptors 10, according to studies. Many PRRs are involved in MetS mechanisms. TLRs and NLRs, on the other hand, are the most well-studied of this pathology 8. Only a few human studies have looked into the function of these receptors in MetS. As a result, the majority of the research presented in this paper was done on murine animals. Many ligands involved in MetS pathways have been proposed to have the ability to initiate the innate immune response 8,13. However, the ligands that activate these receptors and the mechanisms by which they do so remain unclear.

TLRs are membrane proteins that contain a ligand-binding leucine-rich repeat (LRR) domain, a transmembrane helix, and a carboxy-terminal intracellular signaling domain 14. Except for TLR3, TLR7, TLR8, and TLR9, which are located in the endosome 14, these receptors are found in the cell membrane. TLRs are active in the inflammatory processes associated with MetS 8,15, in addition to mediating innate immunity. TLRs recruit adaptor proteins through the MyD88-dependent and MyD88-independent pathways (TRIF-dependent) 16 after they have been activated. TLR3 is the only TLR that can only signal via the MyD88-independent pathway, while TLR4 can signal through all downstream pathways 16. TLRs can control early NF- κ B activation and MAPK stimulation through the MyD88-dependent pathway 17. The MyD88-independent pathway, on the other hand, causes late-phase NF- κ B activation and type I interferon synthesis 17.

NLRs are the main protein receptors in the cytoplasm of mammals, and they play an important role in both innate and adaptive immunity 18. There are twenty-two NLR genes in humans (18,19). These receptors are classified by their role in inflammasome assembly, signaling transduction, transcription activation, and autophagy 20 and have a central NOD (NACHT: NAIP, CIITA, HET-E, and TP-2), a stretch of carboxyl-terminal LRR motifs, and the effector domain in the N-terminal 19. For the purposes of this study, will only look at NOD1, NOD2, and NLRP3 pathways since they are the most well-studied NLRs in MetS 8 mechanisms. Both NOD1 and NOD2 receptors have been shown to trigger NF- κ B stimulation and increased MAPK activity 20,21. The NLRP3 protein is responsible for sensing metabolic stress and assisting in the development of the inflammasome 22, a multimeric protein complex. It's worth noting that other NLRs can also activate this complex (See Ref. 23 for review). When this inflammasome is formed, caspase-1 is activated, and inflammatory cytokines (such as IL1 and IL-18) are released 22. While the proteins recruited or regulated by TLRs and NLRs in response to PAMPs or DAMPs are very different, the ultimate triggered pathways are very similar and include the secretion of inflammatory mediators as well as elevated oxidative stress, both of which contribute to the pathophysiology of the MetS 7, 8, 9 risk factors.

III. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRRS AND METS PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

It's crucial to look at the mechanisms involved in innate immunity to better understand how PRRs deal with the pathophysiology of MetS. PAMPs and/or DAMPs cause abnormal innate immunity activation (TLRs and NLRs), which leads to the pathological processes of this group of diseases and helps to cross the gap between inflammation and metabolic disorders. 5.7.8. TLRs and NLRs regulate the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines through the NF- κ B signaling pathway 24. In addition, the NF- κ B pathway can promote the development of a variety of anti-apoptotic factors, chemokines, and adhesion molecules 24. As a result, inflammation may be recognized as an important risk factor for a variety of diseases, and recent research indicates that PRRs (TLRs and NLRs) may play a significant role in the recruitment and activation of these molecules 25,26.

TLR1, TLR2, and TLR4 levels are the most prevalent in human atherosclerotic lesions, according to Edfeldt and collaborators 27, who discovered that out of nine human TLRs, TLR1, TLR2, and TLR4 levels are the most prominent in human atherosclerotic lesions with consequences in plaque development. TLR7 levels are upregulated in human adipose tissue 28, and TLR3 deficiency in mice affects triglyceride metabolism and glycemic regulation 29, according to other reports. In a mouse model of obesity, TLR3 loss of function increases glucose tolerance while reducing liver steatosis 30. Other TLRs, such as TLR6 and TLR8, have also been proposed to play a role in MetS mechanisms, as follows: TLR6 levels have been shown to be higher in the hepatocytes of obese patients with nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) 31, and TLR8 levels have been found to be higher in obese type 2 diabetic patients 32.

TLRs 2 and 4 have been identified as important mediators of insulin resistance, which is at the heart of MetS 8. TLR2 deficiency does, in fact, prevent mice fed a high-fat diet from obesity and adipocyte hypertrophy. These animals also have better insulin sensitivity and lower expression of ERK1/2 33 (extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2). TLR2 deletion also prevents hypercholesterolemia, hepatic steatosis 34, and beta-cell dysfunction 35 in mice. In the case of TLR4, it is modulated in MetS in part by saturated fatty acids 36,37. The role of this receptor in the development of obesity, insulin resistance, and vessel inflammation has been well established 37. TLR4 knockdown in particular tissues, on the other hand, yielded conflicting results. TLR4 mutation in the hypothalamus's arcuate nucleus prevents obesity-related metabolic disorders 38, while TLR4 deletion in the intestinal epithelium increases MetS 39. Furthermore, since both TLR2 and TLR4 mRNA levels are elevated in human monocytes in response to MetS 25, pharmacologically targeting their pathways may be useful for developing new therapeutic techniques to address the condition's complications.

TLR5 and TLR9 have also been proposed to play a part in MetS, but their functions are still unclear. TLR5 deficiency has been shown to modify the gut microbiota in mice, resulting in hyperlipidemia, hypertension, insulin tolerance, and increased adiposity 40. Another group, on the other hand, found that TLR5 knockout does not affect gut microbial composition and that environmental factors can play a role in MetS 41 mechanisms. TLR9 deletion raises body weight, impairs glucose tolerance and insulin resistance, and increases secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines 42, according to Hong and collaborators. TLR9 knockout or pharmacological blockade, on the other hand, increases insulin sensitivity and decreases macrophage aggregation in adipose tissue, according to Nishimoto and colleagues 43. It's worth noting that in animals, full gene deletion or knockdown can result in unintended physiological adaptations and counter-interactions between signaling pathways as a result of compensatory mechanisms.

TLR10's role and potential impact on biological processes have recently been better understood. By fostering the synthesis of 1L-1Ra 44, this receptor has been shown to have anti-inflammatory effects. The anti-inflammatory properties of TLR10 are due to its dimeric properties, which allow it to interact with other TLRs and affect their signaling pathways 45. When ROS 46 was present, TLR10 expression was also increased in the adipose tissue of both obese and type 2 diabetic individuals. TLR10 has also been linked to adipose tissue anatomy in obese people 45. According to the literature, knocking out both NOD1 and NOD2 receptors inhibits inflammation, lipid aggregation, and peripheral insulin resistance in mice fed a high-fat diet 26. Although the NOD1 receptor was shown to be higher in MetS patients' subcutaneous adipose tissue, NOD2 levels were not substantially different between MetS patients and matched controls. The downstream mediators RIP2 and NF- κ B, as well as the cytokine profile, were all significantly higher in this group of 47 patients. In human adipocytes stimulated with iE-DAP (a NOD1-specific ligand), reduced insulin signaling was observed, which was due to increased c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) and impaired insulin receptor substrate 1 phosphorylation 48.

The modification of pro-inflammatory cytokines (pro-IL-1 β and pro-IL-18) into their bioactive forms is the key contributor to MetS problems caused by the inflammasome 22. According to recent research, inflammatory cytokines inflict harm even in limited amounts, and improvements in their synthesis lead to an increase in oxidative stress mediators. 47. Inflammasome assembly also induces pyroptosis, a caspase-1-mediated cell death marked by elevated inflammation 50. DAMPs are introduced into the extracellular environment as part of this mechanism. As a result, it may be a pathway that allows inflammation to increase in a positive feedback loop.

As previously reported, MetS triggers an increase in reactive oxygen species (ROS) activity and, as a result, oxidative stress 51. Diet-induced obesity causes the release of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in a variety of producing enzymes through a range of pathways 52. In the presence of MetS 53, the nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate oxidase (NADPH-oxidase) enzyme can create free radicals, and TLR4 has previously been shown to modulate this enzyme 54. NLRP3, which encourages inflammasome 22 development, could be able to detect ROS. The crosstalk between ROS and NF- κ B 55 is another interesting feature of this analysis. Although the exact nature of this mechanism remains unknown, it has been shown that ROS can influence NF- κ B nuclear translocation via a variety of signaling pathways and that NF- κ B can control ROS activity at the molecular level 55. Furthermore, both ROS and TLR4 influence nitric oxide (NO) concentrations, a vasoprotective molecule 56,57.

This research shows that PRRs (TLRs and NLRs) play a role in the pathophysiology of MetS. These receptors stimulate a network of signalling pathways with overlapping mechanisms and crosstalk associations that could be used to develop new drugs to combat MetS complications. PRRs and gene polymorphisms in MetS PRRs have been suggested to alter PRRs and gene polymorphisms in MetS PRRs, such as those involved in the pathophysiology of MetS 58,59. As a result, they are generating gaps that could have an effect on their everyday behaviors. Although the causes and consequences of gene polymorphisms in humans remain unknown, predicting their patterns may be useful in determining possible MetS and CVD risk factors.

While genetic variants of TLR2 (R753Q) and TLR4 (D299G and TLR4/T399I) have been shown to be unrelated to type 2 diabetes, a TLR2 gene polymorphism has been linked to lower HDL levels in a Mexican population of 60. It's crucial to remember that different variations will have different outcomes. Changes in the TLR4 gene, for example, have been shown to increase the risk of type 2 diabetes in the Chinese Han population 61. Another study discovered that having several versions of the TLR2-Ht4 haplotype SNP in the TLR2 gene protects against diabetes 62. While the TLR4 SNP896 A/G polymorphism has not been related to these conditions, the SNP1350 T/C polymorphism has been linked to a lower frequency of acute myocardial infarction and arterial hypertension. 63

Obesity, as previously said, is a significant factor in the distribution of MetS. Indeed, blocking the inflammatory response associated with visceral fat is a vital strategy for mitigating the pathology's complications. The D299G/T399I TLR4 polymorphism, which is a main component in MetS pathways, has been linked to increased body fat and insulin resistance 64. The TLR2 rs5743708 variant has also been related to morbid obesity 65, which is a much more risky disease for MetS pathogenesis. The nonsense polymorphism (R392X) in TLR5 has been discovered to predispose to type 2 diabetes while defending against obesity 66, which is an intriguing discovery considering that obesity is a recognized risk factor for type 2 diabetes. TLR10 loss-of-function variants linked to SNPs promote inflammation and disease overpowering in patients by improving cytokine synthesis via TLR2 44.

Gene polymorphism in NLRs, like TLRs, results in different patterns based on the variation and receptor involved. In a study performed in a Chinese hospital, the NLRP3 rs10754558 difference was linked to the prevalence of type 2 diabetes in a pediatric population from Northeast Brazil 67 and the presence of type 1 diabetes in a pediatric population from Northeast Brazil 68. Some mutants have been found to have no effect on diabetes resistance, such as rs5112998 and rs12137901. In pre-hypertensive patients, for example, specific haplotypes in the NOD2 receptor locus can be linked to coronary heart disease 69.

Finally, gene polymorphisms in PRRs like TLRs and NLRs can affect outcomes in both healthy and diseased conditions like MetS. Understanding the interaction between PRR gene polymorphisms and metabolic risk factors could lead to a new diagnostic mechanism in genome-wide association studies.

IV. IN METS, THERAPEUTIC METHODS THAT TARGET PRRS ARE BEING DEVELOPED.

Given the increasing proof that PRRs and/or their downstream signaling pathways play a role in the pathophysiology of sterile inflammation, it's no surprise that they've been the focus of numerous studies. Despite the fact that there is evidence that targeting these receptors can help with chronic conditions, we are only now discussing alternative therapeutic targets. In this section, we look at preliminary evidence from ongoing and completed clinical trials in the United States that relate MetS risk factors to innate immunity mechanisms.

Two clinical trials used eritoran tetrasodium, the most commonly used drug to target TLR4 receptors, to study the effects of receptor inhibition. In a randomized placebo experiment, 60 participants of all genders were screened for eritoran. The researchers decided to see whether using this compound to block TLR4 decreases inflammation and increases glucose tolerance in obese type 2 diabetics (NCT02267317). The same study team then looked at whether TLR4 is involved in lipid-induced insulin resistance in non-glucose-tolerant patients (NCT02321111). According to the NIH website, the Phase 2 experiments were all stopped owing to the drug's expiration and a lack of supply from the supplier (clinicaltrials.gov).

TLR4 expression and TLR4-driven signaling were shown to be higher in lean people who were given a non-esterified fatty acid, which has significant effects on human insulin resistance (NCT01740817). Another randomized controlled trial used atorvastatin to treat 42 children with type 1 diabetes and hypercholesterolemia (NCT01236365). LDL-C, apoB, and atherogenic lipoprotein subparticles were all reduced without worsening insulin resistance 70. Statins have been shown to decrease TLR4 activation in animal models 71,72, so these observations are intriguing. Statins are currently approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for lowering LDL cholesterol (www.fda.gov). As a result, this class of medications may be repurposed to treat MetS. Another randomized study (NCT01420328) looked at the efficacy of Vytorin® (ezetimibe and simvastatin) in obese people and discovered that it was efficient. TLR2 and TLR4 expression are reduced, resulting in anti-inflammatory effects 73.

Two interventional studies have been conducted on the inflammasome. In the first study, researchers looked at whether fasting inhibits NLRP3 activation (NCT02122575); they discovered that this intervention may be a novel way to lower blood saturated fatty acid levels. In a prospective cohort study exploring the effect of fasting and refeeding on T-cell destiny, it was discovered that dietary restriction appears to reduce the incidence of atherosclerosis 74. (NCT02719899). Nonetheless, the mechanism of this procedure and its medicinal applicability are uncertain.

These receptors have been widely investigated, and use antibodies, small molecules, and repurposing drugs, in addition to clinical trials. In cultured cells, targeting TLR4 with SPA4, a peptide that binds to surfactant A and antagonizes this receptor, reduced nuclear translocation of NF- κ B and, as a result, secretion of the pro-inflammatory cytokine (TNF- α). TAK-242 (also known as CLI-095 or resatorvid), a cyclohexene inhibitor that attaches to the TIR domain of TLR4 and inhibits the recruitment of protein adaptors (MyD88 and TRIF), avoids elevated blood pressure, cardiac and renal fibrosis, oxidative stress, and phospho-JNK1/2 and NF- κ B in animal models 75, 76, 77.

There is yet to be a clinical intervention that specifically targets the inflammasome. Pharmacological molecules to antagonize or inhibit downstream effectors like anakinra, rilonacept, and XOMA 052 22 are used in the majority of studies targeting this complex. Anakinra, an IL-1 receptor antagonist, increased endothelial function in a diabetes model (streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats) by reducing NADPH-oxidase production, NF- κ B translocation, and the enzymes COX and iNOS 78, as well as blocking the effects of IL-1. As a result, it seems that it may be a possible pharmacological agent for treating MetS complications.

Tiny molecules including Noditinib 1 or GSK'217 79 have been used to target the NOD1 receptor. The downstream effector RIP1 may also be attacked with the specific inhibitor GSK'214. These inhibitors can block NOD1-induced pathophysiological effects, but their consequences for MetS remain unknown. In spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR) 80, it has been documented that lysosomotropic chloroquine impairs TLR9 signaling and thus defends against blood pressure elevations. Hypertension is a MetS comorbidity that tends to be closely connected to TLR pathways, both by TLR9 and TLR4 downstream pathways 13.

Overall, it's becoming apparent that targeting PRRs, whether for treating MetS-related problems or other illnesses, may be a promising solution in situations where conventional medications are unsuccessful. Despite the fact that this review provided proof that these receptors perform crucial roles in MetS pathways, it still has a long way to go in determining the exact molecular modulators in order to prevent unforeseen side effects and full immunosuppression.

The PRRs (TLRs and NLRs) discussed in this study play a role in the pathophysiological pathways linked to MetS risk factors in the literature. Different crosstalk associations are influenced by the receptors and processes involved in these signaling pathways, and they may be used as possible pharmacological strategies to address problems associated with this disease. It seems that stimulation of PRRs induces not only the release of (pro)-inflammatory cytokines but also a rise in oxidative stress, all of which hinder homeostasis and intensify the pathophysiology of MetS. As a result, attacking these receptors may be a novel approach within the complex MetS pathways.

Previously, biomedical manipulation of PRRs was celebrated as an innovative new way to cure chronic diseases. However, it's important to bear in mind that targeting innate immunity may have unexpected effects, owing to the fact that these receptors are the first line of protection in humans against pathogens and often cause adaptive immunity. In this situation, one of the most pressing questions is whether immunomodulators can improve MetS patient performance as compared to conventional pharmacotherapy, which requires FDA-approved medications for isolated risk factors. At this point, it's possible that this technique may be effective for treating patients who don't respond to existing treatments.

V. GENE THERAPY INVOLVES

Improvements in vectors and delivery methods, as well as ongoing research into novel pathways underlying CVD, have aided gene approaches. However, as opposed to rare metabolic disorders, as well as haematological and oncology equivalents, cardiovascular applications lag well behind in scientific translation. This may be due to variations in the disease process's complexity and chronicity. Unlike disease states caused by single genetic variations, most chronic coronary diseases are multifactorial, involving diverse genetic and environmental associations, making gene therapy less effective. Delivering vectors to obtain safe expression in the heart or a weak blood artery has also raised difficulties. Overexpression of the sarcoplasmic-endoplasmic reticulum $Ca^{2+}/ATPase$ (SERCA), a vital regulatory pump, by adenoviral vector in preclinical heart disease models and early phase clinical trials, regulating myocardial calcium homeostasis and contractility, which is related to heart failure, shows some promise. However, in the broader phase II clinical trial Calcium Up-regulation through Percutaneous Administration of Gene Therapy in Heart Disease, no clinical advantage was found (CUPID2). AAV1 neutralizing antibodies is partly to blame for the lack of active SERCA overexpression. ³² No gene therapy strategy has yet been developed to target dysregulated redox signaling. New targets from elegant molecular mechanistic experiments, as well as enhanced gene therapy delivery, such as the use of non-viral, nanoparticle-based DNA delivery discussed below, give new hope.

The activation of pro-angiogenesis pathways by vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is well known. However, increased redox equilibrium has additional advantages, such as decreased NOX behavior and eNOS coupling. VEGF can also stimulate antioxidant pathways activated by nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (NRF-2). ³³ A phase I/II research in patients with serious coronary artery disease showed not only protection but also increased myocardial perfusion following intramyocardial injection of adenoviral VEGF, based on positive preclinical results. ³⁴ It is unclear what role increased redox signaling plays in comparison to direct activation of pro-angiogenesis pathways.

VI. TECHNOLOGY BASED ON NANOPARTICLES

Endogenous antibody resistance, which contributes to reduced viability and effectiveness, as well as the production of tolerance in an uncertain manner, are major obstacles to effective gene therapy delivery via adenoviruses. ³⁵ Nanoparticle technology has opened up new avenues for developing pharmacokinetic profile regulation, organ- and cell-specific targeting, and controlled release for gene therapies and other novel molecular approaches. The word "nanoparticle" refers to a wide variety of nanoscale structures. Drug distribution is a popular use for nanoparticles, since they can be filled with drugs or other small molecules with custom pharmacokinetic profiles. They are resistant to decay and have appealing properties that help to improve tissue targeting and mitigate toxicity. ³⁶

The distribution of VEGF plasmid using a redox-sensitive heparin-loaded polymeric nanoparticle, which results in maximal drug unloading after the nanoparticle reaches the intracellular space, is an example applicable to CVD. ³⁷ Similarly, a redox-sensitive polymer nanoparticle targeting α_2 -adrenergic receptors was used to deliver the eNOS gene for overexpression in the endothelium, especially in the vicinity of atherosclerotic lesions. ³⁸ This method increased endothelial nitric oxide (NO) production in vitro and defended against plaque formation in an atherosclerotic mouse model in vivo. ³⁸ Lipid structures like liposomes were one of the first types of nanoparticles designed for drug delivery, and they proved to be effective at transporting antioxidants through cell membranes. When compared to basic pegylated SOD/catalase, liposomes containing entrapped superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase effectively improved endothelial cellular activation of these enzymes by 44-fold. ⁴⁰ Liposomal-entrapped decreased glutathione given chronically in vivo to atherosclerosis-prone mice dramatically reduced aortic plaque formation ⁴¹, and liposomal coenzyme Q10 (coQ10) attenuated myocardial ischaemia-reperfusion damage in vitro are two examples of cardiovascular ability. ⁴² Metallic, ceramic, and non-metal lattices, on the other hand, have recently shown robust proof-of-concept in targeted cancer therapy and are gaining interest in cardiovascular therapy. ⁴³ miRNA treatments

MicroRNAs (miRNA or miR) are small non-coding nucleotides that regulate translation by causing direct mRNA degradation as well as the development of an RNA-induced silencing complex, a protein complex capable of cleaving miRNA targets. 44

Via putative effects on redox signaling, approximately 40 miRNAs have been reported as playing a role in the development or defense against CVD. 45 Over the last 15 years, antagoMiRs—synthetic oligonucleotides with an antisense sequence that targets the unique miRNA 46—have been a fascinating growth. Several side-chain modifications can help guard against endogenous nucleases while also facilitating binding to the target miRNA. MiRNAs, on the other hand, pose pharmacokinetic problems, since they have a proclivity for accumulating in the liver and kidneys. 47

VII. PEPTIDES AND MICROPEPTIDES

Recent developments in proteomics and bioinformatics, along with whole-genome sequencing, have shown that certain short amino acid sequences, historically mis-annotated as non-coding due to their limited scale, have significant regulatory functions. These micropeptides have been shown to affect cell proliferation, organogenesis, and metabolic activity, and they are becoming more common as therapeutic targets in cardiovascular science. 51 Short open reading frames that encode functional peptides may serve as ligands or signaling molecules on their own or interact with larger regulatory proteins to exert biological effects. 51 Master regulators of SERCA, which are specifically inhibited by the three muscle-specific micropeptides myoregulin, phospholamban, and sarolipin, as well as recently discovered endoregulin and another-regulin, are physiologically important examples in the cardiovascular system. 52 By displacing the SERCA inhibitors, overexpression of a newly discovered dwarf open reading frame, whose subsequent peptide localizes to the sarcoplasmic reticulum membrane, resulted in increased SERCA activity. The increased peak Ca²⁺ transient amplitude and sarcoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺ load that resulted, as well as the decreased time constant of cytosolic Ca²⁺ decay after each round of contraction-relaxation, has therapeutic effects, implying that dwarf open reading frame could be used to improve muscle contractility. 53

The NOX family of enzymes is a possible target for peptide therapies due to the necessary docking of subunits and regulatory peptides. 54 gp91ds-tat, a first-in-class NOX inhibitor, was developed as a first-in-class drug. It has been shown to lower blood pressure in vivo, 55 attenuate vascular endothelial dysfunction, 56 and inhibit O₂• production in insulin-resistant endothelial cells in several preclinical studies. 57 Targeting subunits related to individual isoforms, such as the newly designed NOXA1ds, a peptide developed to completely bind to the NOX-1 docking site for its activating peptide NOXA1, will enhance specificity even further. 58 The small peptide N-acetyl-Ser-Asp-Lys-Pro (Ac-SDKP) has been shown to have angiogenic and antifibrotic activity, in part by functioning as an angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor 59, and has been shown to protect against fibrosis and myocardial dysfunction in preclinical models. 60 The discovery of micropeptide regulator of-oxidation (MOXI) as a conserved muscle-enriched protein localized to the inner mitochondrial membrane has opened up new avenues for therapies to modulate mitochondrial metabolism and energy homeostasis 61 with relevance to redox signaling in heart failure.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The metabolic syndrome (MetS) is a major factor in the development of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) In the United States, nearly 34% of people in this age group are affected by this condition. Inflammatory pathways are clearly present in abdominal obesity, and inflammation is one of the main mechanisms discovered in MetS patients. This means that the body has launched an immune response, likely caused by the activation of pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) PRRs are responsible for identifying infectious infections in the body and are found in innate immune cells. TLRs are membrane proteins that contain a ligand-binding leucine-rich repeat (LRR) domain, a transmembrane helix, and a carboxy-terminal intracellular signaling domain. TLRs are active in the inflammatory processes associated with MetS 8,15, in addition to mediating innate immunity. It's crucial to look at the mechanisms involved in innate immunity to better understand how PRRs deal with the pathophysiology of MetS. Research indicates that PRRs (TLRs and NLRs) may play a significant role in recruitment and activation of these molecules. TLR1, TLR2, and TLR4 levels are the most prevalent in human atherosclerotic lesions. TLRs 2 and 4 have been identified as important mediators of insulin resistance, which is at the heart of MetS.

TLR10's role and potential impact on biological processes have recently been better understood. By fostering the synthesis of 1L-1Ra, this receptor has been shown to have anti-inflammatory effects. MetS triggers an increase in reactive oxygen species (ROS) activity and, as a result, oxidative stress. The modification of pro-inflammatory cytokines into their bioactive forms is the key contributor to MetS problems caused by the inflammasome. Research shows that PRRs (TLRs and NLRs) play a role in the pathophysiology of MetS. These receptors stimulate a network of signalling pathways with overlapping mechanisms and crosstalk associations. The causes and consequences of gene polymorphisms in humans remain unknown. Predicting their patterns may be useful in determining possible MetS and CVD risk factors.

In MetS, therapeutic methods that target TLR4 receptors are being developed. There is evidence that targeting these receptors can help with chronic conditions. In this section, we look at preliminary evidence from ongoing and completed clinical trials in the U.S. that relate MetS risk factors to innate immunity mechanisms. Statins are currently approved by the Food and Drug Administration for lowering LDL cholesterol. These receptors have been widely investigated, and use antibodies, small molecules, and repurposing drugs. Small molecules including Noditinib 1 or GSK/217 79 have been used to target the NOD1 receptor. Hypertension is a MetS comorbidity that tends to be closely connected to TLR pathways, both by TLR9 and TLR4 downstream pathways.

Biomedical manipulation of PRRs was celebrated as an innovative new way to cure chronic diseases. It's possible that this technique may be effective for treating patients who don't respond to existing treatments. Most chronic coronary diseases are multifactorial, involving diverse genetic and environmental associations. No gene therapy strategy has yet been developed to target dysregulated redox signaling. Technology based on nanoparticles can be used for gene therapy delivery via adenoviruses.

Nanoparticle technology has opened up new avenues for developing pharmacokinetic profile regulation. Lipid structures like liposomes were one of the first types of nanoparticles designed for drug delivery. Metallic, ceramic, and non-metal lattices have recently shown robust proof-of-concept in targeted cancer therapy and are gaining interest in cardiovascular therapy. The word "nanoparticle" refers to a wide variety of nanoscale structures. Peptides and micropeptides have been shown to affect cell proliferation, organogenesis, and metabolic activity. They are becoming more common as therapeutic targets in cardiovascular science. The NOX family of enzymes is a possible target for peptide therapies due to the necessary docking of subunits and regulatory peptides. Small peptide N-acetyl-Ser-Asp-Lys-Pro (Ac-SDKP) has shown to have angiogenic and antifibrotic activity, in part by functioning as an angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor. Nanomedicine applying gene therapy strategies 165-176 have elegant endeavour for treatment of various gene polymorphisms and mutations of complex disorders 177-191.

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